

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRP AND CFRTP AFTER RECYCLING

H. Zushi¹, T. Odai¹, I. Ohsawa¹, K. Uzawa¹ and J. Takahashi¹

¹ *Department of Environmental and Ocean Engineering, The University of Tokyo
7-3-1, Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo 113-8656, Japan*

SUMMARY: World energy consumption will grow rapidly due to Chinese motorization. By life cycle assessment (LCA) of an automobile, percentage of the energy consumption by automobiles in use-stage is about 86% of the total stage. It is important to reduce the weight of an automobile to improve the fuel efficiency. Automobile weight reduction can be achieved in a variety of ways. We considered replacing steel automotive components with carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTP). We approached that CFRTP is molded in press forming without vacuum assist to respond the rapid stamping mass production. We evaluated the recyclability of CFRTP, especially isotactic polypropylene, acrylonitrile butadiene styrene, polycarbonate and polyethylene terephthalate resins to a matrix of the thermoplastic composites.

KEYWORDS: 3R, CFRP, modification of carbon fiber, thermoplastics resin, maleic anhydride, automobile, Chinese motorization, energy consumption

INTRODUCTION

For more than a century many physical futures of the global system have been growing rapidly. For example, population, food production, industrial production, consumption of resources, and pollution are all growing, often more and more rapidly. It is called exponential growth. [1] We study a consumption of resources by the car-orientated society among them. World energy consumption will grow rapidly due to Chinese motorization as described in a subsequent section. The drastic lightening of automobiles to mitigate the energy problem is necessary.

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) is an excellent material used in aerospace and motor sports. CFRP will be realized the ultra-lightweight of next generation automotive applications, because of its lightweight (density of about 1.6 g/cm³), high specific strength, high specific rigidity, and design flexibility. The fuel consumption can be dramatically improved by weight reduction using CFRP. Conventional CFRP, which is molded in autoclave, resin transfer molding (RTM), or vacuum assist resin infusion (VARI) using thermoset resins, has high quality and good performance. However, conventional CFRP is very costly and need considerable time before it can be applied. Next generation CFRP for automotive applications must solve its low cost, high production speed and recyclability. Therefore, it is reduced a half of carbon fiber volume fraction to cheapen its price and is chosen thermoplastic resins as its matrix to improve the recyclability and the repair capability. In addition, we approached that carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics called CFRTP is molded in press forming without vacuuming to respond the speedy stamp production.

In this paper, we presented the mechanical properties of CFRTP after recycle using thermoplastic resins. We showed the possibility of CFRTP recycling to use it for a long time. This is based on 3R rules. 3R means that; reuse with the repair one, reduce of the resources consumption, and recycling on the saving energy consumption. Generally, 3R of lightweight metals such as high tensile steel, aluminum, magnesium, titanium alloys, are difficult. Thus, if the recyclability of CFRTP is better those, CFRTP can be a dominant lightweight material for automotive applications to compete against those on 3R rules, we considered. We presented our vision of recycled CFRTP in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Recycling vision of composite for automotive applications

CHINESE MORIZATION

Method

The transport sector has a close relation to the energy consumption. In addition, by life cycle assessment (LCA) of an automobile, percentage of the energy consumption by automobiles in use-stage is about 86% of the total stage. So, increasing the number of automobiles in non-OECD countries is grown the global energy consumption.

We assume that China is fastest and greatest motorization country in non-OECD countries compared with the past [2]. Chinese motorization was predicted the logistic function presented in equation (1).

$$Y[t] = \frac{\chi}{1 + (\chi - 1)e^{-\mu(t - \tau_0)}} \quad (1)$$

Here, the parameters to predict it; Y is the number of automobiles per 1,000 persons, t is a year, χ is saturated number of automobiles in advanced nation, μ is spreading speed of automobiles and τ_0 is starting year of spreading one. The conditions of the parameters are; χ is 500 by advanced nation that have started the motorization, μ is 0.142 by the statistics data in Japan [3] and τ_0 is 1988 by the statistics data of automobiles in China.

Prediction of the number of automobiles in China

Figure 2 shows about a result of the prediction of the number of automobiles in China. In this figure, in 2014, the number of automobiles in China is about 55 million cars as well as the present in the Japanese currently. In 2020, it explosively grows, and in 2040, it is about 550

million cars as well as the present in the world currently. How the energy consumption will be saved with automobiles society in China, we estimate.

Increase of energy consumption due to Chinese motorization

Figure 3 shows about three simulations of the energy consumption by automobiles in China. In this figure, referred case was considered scenario A1T in IPCC's prediction [4]. In the conditions of scenario A1, the population is not quite growing and China achieve spectacular economic growth. Scenario A1T included scenario A1 assumes the society that leads the technology to consume the energy with high efficiency. The technology to consume the energy with high efficiency includes the spread of diesel hybrid cars and fuel cell electric vehicles (FCEV). However, each technology is not effective, if the automobile weight reduction is not achieved. In Figure 3, the condition of optimism case is assumed that the spread of diesel hybrid and the lightening automobiles are concurrently started from 2015 and the spread of FCEV is started from 2040. The condition of pessimism case is assumed that the scenario which the measures were taken slowly, such as first the diesel hybrid is introduced from 2020, next the lightening automobiles is introduced from 2030, and FCEV is introduced from 2040. In addition, a ratio of 2 to 1 is the ratio of spread speed between optimism and pessimism.

In Figure 3, we can see what the gap between optimism and pessimism is wide in 2050. Thus, the effect of energy saving acutely depends on the timing of introduction and the speed of spread.

In 2050, in pessimism, annual energy consumption by automobiles in China can save about 180 Mtoe (mega tonnes oil equivalent) that is about one-thirds of energy consumption in referred case. In optimism, it is about 30 Mtoe that is about one-twentieths in referred case. The ratio of integrated energy consumption until 2050 between optimism and pessimism is 0.352. It is important to introduce the technology of high fuel efficiency into automobiles, immediately.

In 2050, by IEA [5], the prediction of world energy consumption is about 18,000 Mtoe, of which the transport sector is about 6,000 Mtoe that is one-thirds of the world energy consumption. We completed the world prediction about the energy consumption in transport sector. Only measure of automobiles, it can be saved to three-fourths and two-thirds of total by pessimism and optimism cases.

Figure 2: Prediction of the number of automobiles in China

Figure 3: Increase of the energy consumption due to Chinese motorization

PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENT OF AUTOMOTIVE COMPONENTS

Automobile weight reduction can be achieved in a variety of ways, such as automobile downsizing, redesigning the automobile architecture (e.g., using space frame structure instead of traditional body-in-white structure), using lightweight materials, redesigning existing components with thinner gage sheets and reducing the number of components [6]. Among them, we remark using CF/TPs for the lightweight materials in automotive components. The environmental burdens of automobiles can be mitigated by the 3R i.e., reuse, reduce, and recycle of material which needs for the sustainable car-oriented society.

The drastic reduction of automobile weight can only be archived through using composites to the structural members and panel components. Thermosetting matrix composites reinforced with GF and/or CF which applies to aerospace and formula 1 has excellent specific strength and rigidity. Especially, CFRP is the most trusted ultra lightweight material for the impact resistance [7]. However applying CFRP to automotive components is so difficult due to the number of reasons i.e., it is too expensive material, lack the data of its long-term property and is poor design experience in the automotive area [8]. The other major factor is the long processing time with thermosetting matrix composites witch is also the reason of their high processing cost relative to conventional stamping operation used for steel and aluminium alloys [6].

The advantages of using a thermoplastics polymer instead of a thermosetting polymer as the matrix resin are recyclability, weldability and shorter processing time [6]. The most important issues related to the selection of CF/TPs as automotive components are cost and performance. The cost of CFRP is added material cost to processing cost. These costs can be reduced by using the thermoplastic resins and lessening the fiber volume fraction in composite.

EXPERIMENT

Materials and Methods

Carbon fiber model T700SC-24K was supplied by TORAY Industries, Inc., Japan. Isotactic polypropylene resin (i-PP) and Polycarbonate resin (PC) were purchased by IDEMITSU Kosan Co. Ltd., Japan. Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene resin (ABS) was purchased by

TORAY Industries, Inc., Japan. Polyethylene terephthalate resin (PET) was purchased by TEIJIN Co. Ltd., Japan. The properties of each material were showed in Table 1.

We have investigated the method for recycling of conventional CFRP and CFRTP that is effective both of them. In this paper, we showed the CFRTP recycling method. This method is not only applied to recycling of CFRTP but also recycling of conventional CFRP.

Maleic anhydride was grafted to i-PP to improve the interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and i-PP. The combination ratio is 0.3 wt.% of a composite. Carbon fiber was modified with chemical washing to free its bundle.

The molding process and condition is showed in Table 2. The composite was passed the three-processes such as shredding, mixing and kneading, and molding. We used the shredding machine, “Good Cutter” showed in Figure 4, to shred the composite. The mixing machine as shown in Figure 5, LABO PLAST MILL model 10C100, TOYOSEIKI SEISAKU-SYO, Ltd., is used to mix and knead the shredded composite and resin.

Figure 4: Photograph of shredding machine, “GOOD CUTTER”

Figure 5: Photograph of mixing machine, “LABO PLAST MILL model 10C100”

Table 1: Material properties

material	manufacturer	grade type	density g / cm ³	MFR g / 10 min	E_L, E GPa	$\sigma_{L,f}, \sigma_f$ MPa
carbon fiber	TORAY	T700SC	1.80		230	4,900
i-PP	IDEMITSU	J3000GP	0.90	30.0	2.2	58
ABS	TORAY	TOYOLAC	1.05		2.3	70
PC	IDEMITSU	R1900	1.20	22.8	2.3	90
PET	TEIJIN	TR-8580HP	1.34		3.0	127

Table 2: Molding conditions

composite	mixing and kneading			press molding		remarks
	temp. °C	rev. RPM	time, min	temp. °C	Pressure MPa	
CF / i-PP	200	40	2	200	35	maleic anhydride 0.3wt.%
CF / ABS	220					
CF / PC	300					
CF / PET	300					

Remolding Conditions

The methods for recycling of thermoplastic resins are wide-ranging. In this method, especially, the recycling of thermoplastic products was typically passed 6 processes i.e., recovery, shredding, remove of impurities, decomposition to monomers, re-polymerization and remolding. However, in case of CFRTP, it is so difficult to recycle CFRTP that carbon fibers become the impurities which declines the qualities of CFRTP. It may be the technology which removes the long carbon fiber, but technology consumes much energy and also needs many processes. Thus, this recycling method do not use to CFRTP for the reasons of higher environmental burden and very costly. Consequently, we have investigated the recycling process which is remolded by heat fusion only. We developed the recycling system as shown in Figure 6. In the developed method, the recycling CFRTP products were passed easy 4 processes i.e., recovery, shredding, mixing and kneading, and remolding. It is the method which can procure the recycled CFRTP with energy saving, shorter process and rapid production. Carbon fibers in CFRTP become short fiber which carbon fiber is cut by shearing force in kneading of the recycle. The properties of CFRTP decline to the matrix resin, when fiber length is shorter than limit of one. At last, the products from recycled CFRTP are made by injection molding, and the products are used to conventional plastic products. In this research, the revolution of screw of the mixture is 40 rpm to save the shearing force and to keep the length of fibers for a long time use. There are 6 types of the automotive applications such as following i.e., platform, shafts, structural parts which need the rigidity, strength parts which need the strength, panel components like a roof, bonnet and spoiler, interior parts, and exterior parts like bumper skirt.

Figure 6: Recycling processes for CFRTP and CFRP in just 3.5 hours

CFRP have used to shafts and panel components in very expensive cars. Thus, we can propose the suggestion what closed recycling system optimally separate the recycled materials to use in automotive applications for a long time. This is not cascade recycle. It is originality that the material life fully finishes in a same automobile.

Mechanical Testing

Flexural tests were performed on a testing machine, SHIMAZU Corporation model DCS-10T, using the three-point bending method as per ASTM D790-02 standard. The specimens were tested at a rate of 5mm per a minute. The specimen size is 100 mm x 15 mm x 2 mm of the length, the width and the depth.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the following, we present the result of the flexural properties of recycled CFRTP. In each figures, the property of referred data shown the bar of white is theoretical value. Then, the property of CFRTP is the ideal property on the bending which the long fiber is oriented in the random direction in the composite. Our target of flexural properties is 20 GPa above of modulus and 200 MPa above of strength, which is a property of applied GFRP parts into a present automobile.

Investigation of recycled CF/i-PP

We molded CF/i-PP that is the composite mixed carbon fiber and isotactic polypropylene of the thermoplastic of olefinic. The past our research, such as reference [9], it is better that the large melt mass flow rate (MFR) of i-PP is used, because it improve its soaking into composite itself. Thus, the MFR used i-PP is 30 that is three times of general i-PP. The recycling tests were completed until three-cycles. The flexural modulus is not decreased, but the flexural strength is decreased a little. Likely, this cause is what added maleic anhydride into i-PP was deteriorated by the heat history of mixing and molding. The fiber volume fractions of CF/i-PP are 15% and 30%, and a bending test was conducted about both of them. The way of 15%, it became which was rich in the toughness by a characteristic of i-PP. We jugged what the fiber volume fraction of CFRTP is 30% to the elevatory modulus and rigidity. The discriminative fracture of i-PP was shown after the peek load of CF/i-PP composite. The material dispersion appeared, when the fiber volume fraction is raised. But, this dispersion converges, when the recycling stage is repeated. It is future works that eliminates the dispersion and improves the quality. The flexural modulus of recycled CF/i-PP is about 12 GPa, and the flexural strength is 100 MPa above as shown in Figure 7. The following all performance is investigated in 30% of the fiber volume fraction.

Investigation of recycled CF/ABS

We molded CF/ABS that is the composite mixed carbon fiber and ABS of thermoplastic of styrenic. The performance of recycled CF/ABS was improved by recycling, because the interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and ABS resin has been strong on the ground that the cyclic mixture was impregnate carbon fiber with ABS. We reconsider the management of the temperature, torque and rpm in the mixture process. The fracture ductility progressed. The flexural modulus is about 12 GPa, and the flexural strength is about 120 MPa as shown in Figure 8.

Investigation of recycled CF/PC

We molded CF/PC that is the composite mixed carbon fiber and polycarbonate of engineering thermoplastic resin. The performance of recycled CF/PC was not deteriorated by our recycling method. The failure strain is 1.0% above, and it will become a high-performance

CFRTP. The flexural modulus is about 12 GPa, and the flexural strength is 120 MPa above as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 7: Flexural properties of recycled CF/i-PP at $V_f=15\%$ (upper) and $V_f=30\%$ (lower)

Figure 8: Flexural properties of recycled CF/ABS

Investigation of recycled CF/PET

The performance of recycled CF/PET is extremely poor. The matrix resin of PET was deteriorated by the hydrolysis because CF/PET was mixed and molded at 300 degree in the air atmosphere. In addition, the fiber volume fraction of molding was decreased. We reconsider the management of the temperature and the atmosphere in the mixture and the molding

process. The recycled material is rigid and brittle. The failure strain so minimum, 1.0% below, that the strength is very low. The flexural modulus is about 16 GPa, and the flexural strength is about 65 MPa as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 9: Flexural properties of recycled CF/PC

Figure 10: Flexural properties of recycled CF/PET

CONCLUSION

We investigated the recyclability of CFRTP. We proposed the novel method of recycling CFRTP. The flexural properties of recycled CFRTP are about 12GPa above of the elastic modulus and about 100MPa above of the strength each composites on this method. The elastic modulus is half of the virgin one. The strength is one-thirds of the virgin one. We concluded the reason what occurred the breaking and inflecting of fibers in mixing and kneading process. It is better that fiber volume fraction of recycled composite is low from the recyclability. CF/PC and CF/PET based on the matrix of engineering thermoplastics is not suitable for recyclable CFRTP to deteriorate the performance after recycling. CF/i-PP and CF/ABS based on the matrix of olefinic or styrenic thermoplastics resin, in which there are comparatively a little performance degradation will be expected in future. From our result, CF/i-PP which is the composite of olefinic matrix is promising as CFRTP which it is synthetically judged from cost, productivity, workability (e.g., it is molded at the

low temperature, 200 degrees, comparatively), repairabilities and future capability, etc. CF/i-PP will be realized the ultra-lightweight of practical automotive applications, because of its lightweight (density of about 1.17 g/cm³), design flexibility, good cost performance, and better recyclability. However, the performance of recycled CFRTTP is not yet adequate, when it is applied into the automotive components. It is available to use in the performance of rigidity, but it leave room for improvement in the performance of strength.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

One of the authors (H. Zushi) was supported through the 21st Century COE Program, "Mechanical Systems Innovation," by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports Science and Technology.

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